

TEACHING ENGLISH IDIOMS IN CONTEXTS

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Annontatsion: Should we or shouldn't we teach English idioms to ESL students? Although it is uncommon for ESL students to use them comfortably and effectively, if we choose to not teach them idioms, they'll be missing an important cultural element of the language they strive to speak fluently. However, it stands to reason that idioms should be taught to upper-intermediate or advanced students, individuals who are ready to take their English fluency to the next level.

Key words: fluency, idioms, Most, remember

To make sure that the time you spend teaching idioms is not time wasted, follow these steps and instructions:

Choose 5 to 8 idioms that may be easily grouped

Most idioms fall into simple categories, like idioms with animals or parts of the body. Choose 5 to 8 from any category, for example idioms with time. If you choose more than 10, you'll only succeed in overwhelming your students, and they won't remember any of the idioms they saw in class. So, to teach idioms with time, you may teach the 8 idioms found in this worksheet called **Time Flies When You're Having Fun**. Before presenting the idioms, make sure students understand that they are usually used in spoken English, and rarely in written form, with some exceptions (they are widely used on the Internet, in blogs, ezine articles, etc...but students must understand that their use is informal).

Introduce idioms in context, never in isolation

Some ESL teachers simply go over a **list of English idioms** and their definitions or explanations. However, to ensure that students not only understand them, but also

learn to use them, present idiom examples in context, for example, in simple conversations where the meaning of the idiom is clear. To introduce the idiom *to give someone a hard time*, present a conversation like this one:

- Juan: Hey Sarah, you look sad. What's up?
- Sarah: Well, I didn't play very well today during volleyball practice, and my teammates were not very understanding. They said I was clumsy and had to focus more on the game. They said a 5-year old girl played better than me.
- Juan: Oh! I'm so sorry they gave you such a hard time.

Ask students to guess or figure out the meaning of the idiom. Correct as necessary. Ask them to provide other examples of what it means to give someone a hard time. Then, move on to another conversation for another idiom.

Remember that the goal is to get students to not only understand idioms, but also learn how to use them effectively. Divide the class into pairs. Each pair of students gets one or two idioms to work with. They must write a conversation and use this idiom in it. Walk around the classroom to assist students and check for accuracy.

Teaching Idioms Is Teaching Fluency

Colorful language and powerful imagery make idioms a lot of fun for ESL learners. When you throw cats and dogs in a scene where they are falling from the sky, it's hard to know exactly what a phrase might mean. It's almost like a code-breaking game, where students must learn that when certain words come together in a phrase, they can mean something very different.

It's important to not only teach the meaning of idioms, but to also teach how to use them correctly and effectively. When a non-native speaker uses an idiom correctly, he or she will sound very fluent. But, on the other hand, if they bumble the phrase, they will sound the exact opposite.

Learning idioms is appropriate for intermediate to advanced students. If you teach an idiom lesson to beginners or low-intermediate learners, you may well be

putting them in the bumbling category mentioned above. Teach idioms wisely and sparingly to ensure your students' success.

Tips for Teaching English Idioms Wisely

Provide idioms in context, so students can fully understand the meaning. Be sure to provide a sample conversation around it. For example, take the following dialogue featuring the idiom “to be a chicken” when at a local amusement park.

Jack: Ooh, wow. Look at that roller coaster, Jane! It goes upside-down!

Jane: My stomach aches just looking at it. I will not ride that.

Jack: Ah, come on. *Don't be a chicken!*

Watching videos of native speakers conversing is a great way to give your students demonstrations on how idioms are used in the real world. FluentU is a great resource that can help you highlight the usage and context of the various idioms used to your students.

FluentU takes authentic videos—like music videos, movie trailers, news and inspiring talks—and turns them into personalized language learning lessons.